

Rethinking exemplification in mathematics teacher education multilingual classrooms

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Examples that teachers choose and use are fundamental to what mathematics is taught and learned, and what opportunities for learning are created in mathematics classrooms. In this paper, I bring together three frameworks which have been used separately in mathematics education research – variation theory, meaning making as a dialogic process framework, and the notion of interacting/multifarious facets/dimensions within teacher education. The emergent framework consists of a triadic approach to understanding exemplifying practices within teacher education, and in particular, within multilingual teacher education classrooms. Lesson transcript data from an introductory class in probability in one teacher education multilingual classroom is used to illustrate how working with the amalgamated framework conduces to a powerful way of examining the choice and use of examples in mathematics teacher education multilingual classrooms, and how the three frameworks work together to attend to three critical layers involved in the complexity of teaching and learning in mathematics teacher education multilingual classrooms.

Introduction

As a teacher educator involved with both pre-service and in-service teacher education (TE), I have often tried to model how to teach using different practices in my class. These practices in themselves were never the object of attention in our discussions beyond their mere definitions. I became more sensitised to the importance of engaging my students on what makes for a good practice in multilingual classrooms in the course of my study (See Essien, 2014) using Wenger's (1998) communities of practice theory to engage with teacher preparedness for teaching mathematics in multilingual pre-service teacher education classrooms. Subsequently, how teacher educators in multilingual classrooms choose and use examples – that is, exemplifying as a practice – became an important focus of my research and practice. The importance of mathematical examples – that is, of tasks which are used to illustrate concepts in mathematics (Essien, 2021) – cannot be overemphasised. My focus on exemplifying as a mathematics practice was motivated by the centrality of examples in the teaching and learning of mathematics. Research has shown that the examples which teachers choose and how these examples are used play an important role in what mathematics is taught and how students learn and understand the mathematics that is taught in class

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(Arzarello, Ascari, & Sabena, 2011; Bills, Dreyfus, Mason, Tsamir, Watson, & Zaslavsky, 2006; Goldenberg & Mason, 2008; Zaslavsky, 2010; Zodik & Zaslavsky, 2008).

In my attempt to better understand the choice and use of examples, the following questions became important: what examples can teachers use in multilingual mathematics classrooms to help mediate knowledge in mathematics? And fundamentally, how can pre-service teachers be enculturated into how to choose and use examples that would help their future (multilingual) students better understand mathematics? What affordances do the selection and use of examples offer to pre-service teachers regarding the multiple dimensions of TE in mathematics? And what should a “good” (use of) example be in multilingual pre-service teacher education mathematics classrooms – given that these pre-service teachers themselves are most likely to teach in multilingual classrooms at the end of their qualifications? While it is not the intention of this paper to answer all the above questions, these questions were, for me, the driving force behind my quest for an all-encompassing framework which has the ability to not only provide a gaze into the types of examples that are chosen and used within TE, but also a gaze into how the choice and use of examples in teacher education can attend to the complexity involved in enculturating pre-service multilingual teachers into the intricacies of teaching in multilingual mathematics school classrooms. In doing this, the words of Lester (2010, p. 83) who argues that “rather than adhering to one particular theoretical perspective, [that] we act as bricoleurs by adapting ideas from a range of theoretical sources to suit our goals”, came to mind. In an earlier paper for ZDM (Essien, 2021), I attempted to do this using a dyadic framework that accounted for both the examples chosen and used and the interactional pattern during the enactment of the examples. My contention is that using the dyadic framework did not account sufficiently for how pre-service teachers (PSTs) were enculturated into the multifaceted dimensions within teacher education.

In analysing the nature of examples used in mathematics classrooms, variation theory as a theory of learning has become ubiquitous in research about how the structure of an example space is not only an important mathematical process but also a critical didactical goal (Arzarello et al., 2011). This paper is premised on the notion that variation theory, which is commonplace in research involving the choice of examples in mathematics classrooms, may be insufficient to provide adequate perspectives on the quality of instructional examples (Zaslavsky, 2010) in teacher education classrooms of pre-service teachers who are themselves multilingual and who will teach in multilingual classrooms at the end of their qualification. Using a multifocal framework designed to unpack such complexities, I argue that in order to take into account the full extent of the multifaceted nature of teacher preparation for teaching in multilingual context, exemplifying as a mathematical practice in teacher education needs necessarily to also account for 1) how language is used to enable what some authors (e.g., Stein, Engle, Smith, & Hughes, 2008) have referred to as productive mathematical discussions in the class, and others (e.g., Engle & Conant, 2002) as productive disciplinary engagement, and 2) how the different facets involved in pre-service teachers education are (co-)constructed in multilingual context.

I start the next section by a brief exposition of variation theory subsequently bring in two ‘bricoleurs’, – meaning making as a dialogic process framework and the notion of interacting/multifarious facets or dimensions within TE. Then I present the amalgamated framework. Although this paper is a conceptually rather than an empirically driven piece, using transcribed data of an introductory probability lesson, I show the applicability of the framework (so formed) and discuss the relevance of the framework both conceptually and empirically and how the interactional process in the enactment of examples bring into focus (or not) the multiple dimensions characteristic of teacher education in multilingual contexts.

Variation theory in mathematics teaching and learning

There have been several theoretical expositions on variation theory as a pedagogic theory in mathematics classrooms (see Kullberg, Runesson, Kempe, & Marton, 2017; Marton & Booth, 1997; Pang & Marton, 2005; Watson & Mason, 2006). For this paper, suffice it to indicate that variation theory holds that learning is a function of discernment, that is, of seeing or experiencing critical aspects of what is to be learned (Marton & Booth, 1997). Three core tenets of variation theory are important to my overall framework: Object of learning, Critical features, and Patterns of variation. The object of learning is what is to be learnt (Pang & Marton, 2005) – it is the focus of attention. In mathematics, this would be the mathematical object of learning. Pang and Marton (2003, 2005) and Runesson (2005) make a distinction between the intended, the enacted, and the lived objects of learning. The intended object of learning is the capabilities the teacher wants the learners to develop and the enacted object of learning is how these capabilities are realised in the classroom. As such, the enacted object of learning “is co-constituted in the interaction between learners and the teacher or between the learners themselves” (Runesson, 2005, p. 70). The lived object of learning is what is actually learned, that is, how the object of learning is experienced by the students. This brings to focus the important role the teacher plays in how his/her chosen examples are used in relation to the context in which the teaching is imbedded so that the intended object of learning aligns as much as possible to the lived object of learning.

Variation theory defines critical features are those aspects of a phenomenon that are necessary for the learner to discern in order for the learner to develop a particular understanding of the object of learning in focus. Variation theory holds that learners own experience of certain patterns of variation and invariance of novel situations and discernment or awareness thereof of the critical features of the object of learning is a *sine qua non* condition of learning. This means that discernment is not possible without the experience of difference between two of more different things/situations and without the experience of difference, it would not be possible to discern similarities. The kinds of awareness brought about by patterns of variation include contrast, separation, generalisation and fusion. Regarding contrast, variation theory holds that learners are more readily able to discern the critical features of an object if they are able to contrast it with other objects or another object. Similarity is what is kept invariant (Watson & Mason, 2006) in the mathematics structure within the sequence of mathematics examples. Drawing on Marton

and Tsui (2004), Olteanu and Olteanu (2013) assert that separation “refers to the other dimensions of variation that need to be kept invariant or varying at a different rate in order to discern a dimension of variation that can take on different values” (p. 515). Variation theorists argue that in order to fully understand a concept, it is necessary to also experience varying features of the concept so as to separate the features that are not critical (that is, that are not defining features of the concept). Fusion is when there is simultaneous variation of several critical aspects of the object of learning in an example space (Lo & Chik, 2016; Olteanu, 2018). The interrelationship between the different constructs of variation theory is represented in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: How the various concepts in variation theory interconnect

Perhaps, a good way to summarise variation theory is in the words of Lo and Chik (2016, p. 296) who assert that “necessary conditions for learning include focusing on the object of learning [hence the central position occupied by the object of learning in Figure 1], identifying which of its aspects or features are critical, and exposing learners to appropriate patterns of variation that help them discern these critical aspects or features”.

‘Bricolaging’ variation theory

What does it mean to use variation theory in multilingual classrooms? More specifically, how can variation theory be used in multilingual teacher education classrooms so that it accounts for the complexity involved in preparing teachers for teaching in multilingual classrooms?

To better understand the choice and use of examples in teacher education, I draw on Mortimer and Scott’s (2003) notion of meaning making as a dialogic process, and the notion of interacting identities within teacher education (Essien, 2014) and bring these to bear on variation theory. Lo (2012) argues that variation theory has two aspects: “the specific aspect, which refers to the subject matter, knowledge or skill that we wish students to learn (short-term goal), and the general aspect, which refers to the capabilities that can be developed through the learning of the specific aspect (long-term goal)” (p. 25). The long-term educational goal of pre-service teachers needs necessarily to go beyond knowledge acquisition and knowledge of subject matter. In any mathematics classroom, not only are examples used in the teaching and learning process important, but also important is the discourse that is

used to engage with the chosen examples and how language is used to negotiate meaning in the interactional process leading to the construction of the mathematical knowledge and the development of mathematical thought (Jung & Schütte, 2018; Scott, Mortimer, & Aguiar, 2006). Through such interaction, the multiple dimensions within teacher education are attended to (or not) as the class engages with the examples at hand. My use of the term ‘discourse’ resonates with Monaghan’s (2009, p. 15; drawing on Morgan, 2007) understanding of discourse to mean the “patterned uses of language and other forms of communication whose deployment identifies the user as belonging to a particular community at a particular time in a particular setting”. In what follows, I engage with meaning making as a dialogic process.

Meaning making as a dialogic process

Mortimer and Scott (2003) conceive of meaning making as fundamentally a dialogic process, where different ideas are expressed and acknowledged by the teacher, and worked upon. The framework focuses specifically on ways in which the teacher acts in order to guide meaning making interactions within the classroom. The framework comprises of five different, but interconnected aspects of interactions in the classroom 1) teaching purposes; 2) content; 3) communicative approach; 4) patterns of discourse; and 5) teacher interventions. Mortimer and Scott’s framework positions dialogue as connecting participants to meaningful, purposeful and valuable processes of knowledge construction.

In the current framework, I have focused more on the aspects of the framework that deal with classroom interaction, namely, the communicative approach and patterns of discourse as it is my contention that variation theory, in its focus on the object of learning, already engages with the mathematics content within the classroom. It is also my contention that in the mathematics teacher education classroom, the framework on the multifarious dimensions of teacher education (which I engage with in the subsequent section) is more adequate for delineating the ‘teaching purposes’ aspect of Mortimer and Scott’s framework.

Communicative approach focuses on “how the teacher works with students to develop ideas in the classroom” (Mortimer & Scott, 2003, p. 33). For Mortimer and Scott, talk can be dialogic or authoritative, but it can also be interactive or non-interactive. A dialogic talk allows for different points of view even if the talk is orchestrated by one person, while an authoritative talk focuses on one point of view – usually that of the teacher. Talk can also be interactive which means it is structured to allow for the participation of other people, or non-interactive when it excludes the participation of other people. Mortimer and Scott conceive of the meaning making process as two continuums in which in the first continuum, at one extreme there is the dialogic communication approach and at the other extreme, there is the authoritative communication approach (see Scott et al., 2006). In the second continuum, there is interactive talk at one end and non-interactive talk at the other.

Figure 2: The dialogic-authoritative dimensions of discourse on an interactive–non-interactive continuum (adapted from Mortimer & Scott, 2003, p. 35).

The two dimensions of communicative approach (dialogic–authoritative and interactive–non-interactive) can be categorised into four classes of communicative approach with which discourse can be analysed (see Figure 2). The four classes are: 1) *Interactive/dialogic* where the teacher seeks to elicit and explore different ideas about a particular issue or concept and involves the students in the interactional process through, for example, questions which probe students’ points of view; 2) *Non-interactive/dialogic* where the teacher is involved in presenting a specific (mathematics) point of view in a presentational mode (non-interactive), but at the same time, explicitly considering and drawing attention to different points of views (dialogic); 3) *Interactive/authoritative* where the focus is on one specific point of view that leads students through a question and answer routine with the aim of establishing and consolidating that point of view; 4) *Non-interactive/authoritative* which involves the teacher presenting a specific mathematics point of view or concept in a formal lecture mode (Scott et al., 2006).

Each communicative approach is put into action through specific *patterns of discourse* used by the teacher. Mortimer and Scott (2003) introduced the Initiation, Response, and Prompt (I-R-P-) pattern of discourse (Aguiar, Mortimer, & Scott, 2010; Mortimer & Scott, 2003; Scott et al., 2006). They argue that this pattern of discourse can also occur either in form of a closed chain or open chain in the interactional process. For closed chain, the pattern

takes the I-R-P-R-P-R-...E form, where the prompt (P) by the teacher is followed by a further response from the student (R), and so on until the chain is closed by an evaluation (E) by the teacher. In the open chain, there is no final evaluation by the teachers, and so the interactional process takes the I-R-P-R-P-R-P-R- form (Aguilar et al., 2010; Scott et al., 2006). This pattern may be different if students (rather than teachers) are the initiators of the question in the above chain. They pattern would then be in the form I-R_{s1}-R_{s2}-R_{s3}- (where S₁ would be student 1, S₂ student 2, etc). Mortimer and Scott argue that this pattern of discourse can be used to support dialogic interaction while most authoritative interactions are played out through the I-R-E pattern.

Multifaceted dimensions of teacher education

For teachers of mathematics intending to use variation theory in their classrooms, variation theory provides a way of structuring their lessons to maximise the chances of students' lived object of learning aligning as closely as possible to the teacher's intended object of learning. In teacher education multilingual classrooms, however, both the intended object of learning and the lived object of learning are more complex because they both necessarily need to go beyond the acquisition and/or the construction of disciplinary (content) knowledge. Hence, it is not simply about choosing examples that will achieve the target objectives as this could very easily place an emphasis solely on content. In pre-service teacher education mathematics classrooms, in addition to being knowledgeable about the mathematics content the Pre-service teachers (PSTs) will teach at the end of their qualification, PSTs need to develop an awareness of the context in which they will teach and have knowledge about instructional practices that are pertinent for this context. In this vein, research in multilingual classrooms has argued for the need to attend to linguistic aspects of mathematics teaching and learning and for attention to be paid to the language needs of multilingual learners (Barwell, 2020; Erath, Prediger, Quasthoff, & Heller, 2018; Schleppegrell, 2007; Smit & van Eerde, 2011). Moschkovich (2013) and Moschkovich and Zahner (2018) also argue that in mathematics classrooms, attention needs to be paid to enculturating students into participating in valued mathematical practices. In the specific context of teacher education for teaching mathematics in multilingual contexts, it can be argued that the multifacetedness of teacher education necessitates that PSTs need to at once be enculturated into becoming teachers of mathematics, becoming teachers of mathematics in multilingual classrooms, becoming learners of mathematics content, becoming learners of mathematical practices and becoming proficient LoLT Users for the purpose of teaching/learning mathematics (Essien, 2014). My elaboration of these multiple dimensions involved in TE draws from both the field of mathematics education (as indicated above) and from Wenger's (1998) notion of identity as a 'constant becoming', as trajectories which are not necessarily linear, and which has no fixed destination.

Becoming teachers of mathematics is about teaching, and the teacher educator sees herself/himself as developing this dimension within teacher education in the PSTs, while the PSTs see themselves as imbibing this identity. By the same token, in *becoming learners of*

mathematics content, the teacher educator sees herself/himself as responsible for the development of disciplinary knowledge in the pre-service teachers, and the pre-service teachers see themselves as learners of mathematics content. *Becoming learners of mathematical practices* relates to becoming knowledgeable about mathematical processes such as the processes of coming to define, exemplify, code switch, revoice, etc. If, for example, a teacher educator teaches a particular content using her/his chosen examples, and the focus is on the mathematics content, the teacher educator is enculturating the PSTs into becoming learners of mathematics content. But if the focus is also on the logic behind the examples that have been selected for use and what makes for a good set of examples in the topic at hand, then the teacher educator is enculturating the PSTs into becoming learners of mathematical practices/processes. In *becoming teachers of mathematics in multilingual classrooms*, there is something specific about teaching in multilingual contexts, and as such, attention is not only paid to the fact that the pre-service teachers would become teachers, but that they would become teachers in multilingual contexts. *Becoming proficient language users for the purpose of teaching/learning mathematics* describes a situation in which attention is paid to how the mathematics language and the language of learning and teaching (LoLT) in which it (mathematics language) is imbedded, are used in class.

A triadic framework for understanding examples in multilingual classrooms

How do these different frameworks come together to provide a gaze into examples and example spaces used in teacher education multilingual classrooms?

I contend that while variation theory provides perspective into the choice of examples by the teacher educator and the mathematics made possible to learn, Mortimer and Scott's (2003) framework illuminates how language is used to engage with these examples in practice, and finally the framework on the multifarious dimensions within teacher education provides perspective on how through the teacher educator's use of language, these dimensions are either attended to (or not) in teacher education multilingual classrooms. In Figure 3 below, I present the resultant triadic framework.

At the centre of the merger framework is the mathematical object of learning. This is because the object of learning is the focus of attention for the lesson. The teacher educator needs to first determine what the object of learning is for a class, and what critical features within an example set are best suited to achieve her/his object of learning. It is at this point that the patterns of variation become key (hence the question: "what examples would best bring out the critical features" is crucial). But also, it is essential for the teacher educator to engage with the kinds of discourse (patterns of discourse), communicative approach (collectively called interactional process), and teacher moves that are more adequate not only in the teaching process, but also in the discernment of pre-service teachers' understanding of the object of learning. The question as to which combination of interactional process and teacher moves will best enable pre-service teachers to develop a relevance structure on the topic at hand so that learning is made more meaningful to them becomes important.

Figure 3: A triadic framework for understanding examples in mathematics teacher education multilingual classrooms

The bidirectional arrows between the 5 dimensions within TE and the core concepts of variation theory, and those from Mortimer and Scott framework are an indication that through the interactional process in engaging with the examples, multiple facets in TE are attended to (or not). But also, the awareness of the context of teaching and learning and the context the PSTs will teach at the end of their qualifications need to also inform the interactional process in class.

These three frameworks have been used separately by researchers to analyse data. I bring all three frameworks together and show an example (using empirical data) of how it can be used holistically to gain insight into not only the exemplifying practices within teacher education, but into how through the interactional process associated with the examples used in the classroom, opportunities for the enculturation of PSTs into the different facets within TE can be teased out. Zaslavsky (2010) argues that some examples have more explanatory power than others depending on the context and the classroom activities surrounding these examples. In this sense, the amalgamated framework provides tools for analysis of the instructional examples in classrooms which are both pre-service and multilingual in nature. It must be noted that in this framework, the examples that are chosen and used, the pattern of discourse that is enacted need not necessarily be fixed before the lesson.

Using the triadic framework to understand examples in mathematics teacher education multilingual classrooms

In the transcripts that follow, I bring the triadic framework (henceforth ‘the framework’) to bear on the example space used by a teacher educator in an introductory class on probability in order to show the value of the framework in analysing classroom data in multilingual teacher education classrooms. I engage with the classroom interactional process that occurred during the enactment of these examples and also engage with what facets of teacher education were attended to in the course of the enactment. For brief background, the teacher educator is a monolingual first language English speaker and does not share a common first language with most of her PSTs, most of whom are multilingual. It is important to note that as a product of the old South African high school curriculum, the PSTs in this class were encountering the topic probability for the first time, having not done it previously at high school. In the introductory class, focused on teaching the meaning of probability and its scale, the teacher educator provided the class with these four examples:

Example 1: Chances of the teacher educator coming to class in the subsequent lesson

Example 2: Tossing a coin. The game of football is used in which the referee tosses a coin after two captains have chosen their side of the coin

Example 3: Throwing a dice: Throwing a dice and finding:

3.1 $P(4)$

3.2 $P(\text{Even number})$

3.3 $P(\text{number less than } 5)$

Example 4: Pack of cards and finding:

4.1 $P(\text{Jack})$

4.2 $P(10 \text{ Diamond})$

4.3 $P(\text{Odd number})$

4.4 $P(\text{Heart})$

4.5 $P(\text{Black/Suit})$

After this, in the next lesson, the teacher educator performed an experiment involving the law of large numbers and subsequently explained theoretical probability. Due to space limitations, in this paper, using classroom observation transcripts, I focus on the four examples above used in the introductory lesson. Using the merger framework, I start by analysing the example set based on variation theory as it concerns the object of learning, patterns of variation and critical features before engaging with the teacher moves and the interactional process in the enactment phase of the examples.

While this lesson was not theory-driven based on variation theory, a number of observations can be made on the teacher educator’s choice of examples using variation theory as a lens, and in terms of what the examples make possible to learn. First, in considering the set of examples used in this introductory lesson on probability, it can be deduced that even though the initial object of learning was the definition and the meaning of probability at the start of the class, this object of learning shifted to the relevance of probability in everyday context. In terms of variance and invariance, all four examples are similar in the sense that

they relate to (and were taught in such a way that they related to) the PSTs' real-life context. Examples 1 and 2 are also invariant in as much as there are two possible outcomes. What is possible to discern in Examples 1 and 2 is that even though both have two possible outcomes (in terms of probability), the desired outcome can be an "either/or" situation. In Example 1, the teacher educator will either be in class or not be in class, and in Example 2, one captain either wins or loses. But beyond this, the two examples also allow the PSTs to discern the difference between the two scenarios in both examples in that while the probability of coming to class for the teacher educator is either 0 or 1 (for theoretical probability) or dependent on the relative frequency in terms of the number of times the teacher educator has been present/absent from class (relative probability), the probability of either winning the toss or not in Example 2 is $\frac{1}{2}$. The two examples make it possible for the PSTs to be able to discern and generalise that situations of "either/or" are not necessarily 0 or 1 in probability. The question that can be asked here is to what extent the teacher moves and interactional process enabled the PSTs to discern the above from the examples.

What contrasts Example 3 from the first two examples is the fact that there are six possible outcomes in Example 3. In Example 4, the structure of the question is invariant with Example 3 but can also be differentiated by the fact that Example 4 has 52 possible outcomes. Overall, four aspects or dimensions of variation are present across Examples 1 to 4.

Aspects	Examples of Critical Features
Events	Tossing a die, tossing a coin, or Obtaining a particular suit from a pack of cards
Sample Space	Coin: 2; Dice: 6; Cards: 52
Sample points	P(H), P(4) or P(10 diamonds)
Conditions	P(less than four) or P(Black or Suit)

Table 1: Critical features evident in the teacher educator's example set

These are events and their corresponding sample space and/or sample points and the stated conditions around the desired outcomes. The critical features or the values related to these aspects (see Table 1) are different and vary according to the nature of the presented event. So the example space can be described as simultaneously varying and thus Fusion.

So far, my analysis has focused on using variation theory to analyse the examples chosen for the introductory class on probability. In what follows, using transcripts of the interactional process in the class, I show a snippet of how the teacher educator enacted Examples 2 (see Essien, 2021, for analysis of Example 3).

Transcript 1: Tossing the coin

- 1 TE: So for example [*writes: e.g.*] ...has anyone got a coin here please? I didn't bring one in. [*gets a coin*]. Right. We are now about to kick off with the Confederation Cup. I'm the captain of South Africa Bafana Bafana and you [*points to a student*] are the captain of Iraq [*everyone laughs*]. And the referee comes along. Now before that you know that the coin is tossed. What do you call it in your language? How do you call that?

- 2 PSTs: *(Students shout out answers)*
- 3 TE: Anyway, so he [Referee] comes along [*hands the coin to a student*] You are the referee. Now before he does the activity, the referee is going to toss the coin. This is the event. Now whoever gets like a head or a tail, whoever gets it, what happens then?
- 4 PST1: Reward
- 5 TE: Ja, but what is the reward for getting the... you know, if I call 'heads' and she tosses heads
- 6 PST1: Then you get to kick off
- 7 TE: Then I get the kick-off, don't I? OK.
- 8 PST2: Choose sides.
- 9 TE: Now, oh hang on, before you toss the coin, listen to me, what are the chances that heads are going to come up?
- 10 PSTs: [*in chorus*] Half-half
- 11 T: Half-half
- 12 PST3: 2 to 1
- 13 TE: 2 to 1. What else?
- 14 PST2: [*softly*] Unlikely
- 15 PST4: Even odds
- 16 TE: How do we speak?
- 17 PST5: Equally likely
- 18 TE: Equally likely chances that heads will come up. OK, do you see how I'm using the language with the number, with this? What's the number? You said it just now? Choose one of the numbers. [...]
- 19 TE: So basically you can read this in mathematics just like this and immediately, instead of saying, 'Well it's half-half' or 'it's equally likely' what you can do is give me a number that goes with this event. What are the chances of getting heads? So please put equals [*next to P (heads) writes =*]. And after that you said ... [*after = writes ½*] ...It's 1 out of 2 chances. Now I'd like you please to put the 2 in another colour. In fact let's just put the 1 in another colour [*goes over and writes the 1 (numerator) in pink and the 2 (denominator) in yellow*]
- 20 TE: I'm doing this for a reason.
- 21 TE: If you create a fraction like this, people, the numerator... here [*writes N*], the numerator tells me something and the denominator tells me something. [*writes D = with a line pointing to the 2*]. Now think of the coin, think of the ½, the 1 and the 2 and tell me what they tell me. [*TE cleans the scale off the board*]
- 22 TE: You see a half in fraction work we teach the little ones it's 1 out of 2 equal pieces, isn't it? So if I cut an apple into 2, half-half, that's it. In Probability, this fraction is telling me more in English because it's linked to an activity, OK. So what's it telling you? Right, what's the numerator telling me?

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- 23 PST: I think the numerator is telling you that out of the 2 chances available of(?) which(?) the denominator, there's a probability of you getting only one. So of which it can be either the head or the tail.
- 24 TE: OK, so the numerator, do you see that the numerator is linked to what I want?
[points to N and then to heads]. That's very very important you understand that. [...]

In Transcript 1, the teacher educator taught the concept of tossing a coin (the object of learning) as something that is connected to the PSTs' everyday life by first using a physical coin but also by using soccer as an example. Using the triadic framework, it is possible to see how the pattern of discourse and the communicative approach enabled the teacher educator to bring into focus (or not) the different facets of teacher education. Interactive/authoritative approach is clearly the predominant communicative approach in the transcript. As indicated previously, using the interactive/authoritative communicative approach entails that even though the teacher educator welcomes PSTs' viewpoints, the interactional process is directed to one viewpoint – in this case, the viewpoint of the teacher educator. In Turn 9 where the teacher educator asks the PSTs what the chances are of obtaining a Head even before commencing with the experiment of tossing a coin, the teacher educator uses an I-R-P-R-P-R-P-E pattern of interaction to allow for different views to be offered (Turns 12, 14 and 15) on the probability of tossing a coin. The different viewpoints however converge to the teacher educator's viewpoint (hence interactive/authoritative as opposed to interactive/dialogic). It is important to note that through this interactional process, the teacher educator attempts to incorporate cognitive academic language opportunities after noting the PSTs' one- to two-word responses. She therefore asked in Turn 16, *how do we speak?*, and provides the answer in Turns 18 and 19 drawing the PSTs' attention to the correct way of expressing the probability of obtaining a Head when a coin is tossed. By so doing, attention is paid to the development of the PSTs into becoming proficient users of the LoLT.

A parallel is seen later in the transcript where the teacher educator instructor draws on language to explain the meaning of the answer ($1/2$) obtained in the probability question. Here, we see a focus on meaning rather than on procedures (for arriving at the correct answer) where the interactional process around the solution to the example attempts to give meaning to the mathematics symbol. Attention is paid to how the mathematical representation and the register around the mathematics symbol ($1/2$ in this case) are related. Such approach of interweaving content and language is well documented in recent literature (example, Wessel, 2019; Erath et al., 2018). But what the teacher educator does in addition to weaving the content and the mathematical language associated with the content is to draw on both content and the interactional context of the content to, in Turn 22, allude to how fraction is taught in earlier grades thus paying attention to the fact that the PSTs are becoming teachers of mathematics.

Discussions in relation to the triadic framework

Going back to the example space provided by the teacher educator, it is my contention that what the teacher educator could do further in enacting the examples is to focus on explanations that allow for the PSTs to see structure in the example space that makes generality possible. While this generality is evident using variation theory as a lens, in reality, it is mainly through the interactional processes and the teacher moves that this generality can become evident to PSTs. If the teacher educator had drawn attention to the pattern of variation and invariance in the questions she posed, she would have provided opportunity for the development of PSTs as learners of the mathematical practice of exemplifying. This is because in so doing, she would have drawn attention to exemplifying as a mathematical process.

While the framework allows for teasing out which dimensions of teacher preparation for teaching mathematics in multilingual context come into focus, at the same time, it also provides perspectives on which dimensions are backgrounded. In Transcript 1, through the interactional process around the examples at hand, it is easy to see attention paid to (and the PSTs enculturated into) 1) becoming learners of mathematics content, 2) becoming teachers of mathematics, and 3) becoming proficient users of the language of learning and teaching. Using the framework as a lens, it also becomes evident that in the enactment of the mathematical object of learning, becoming teachers of mathematics in multilingual context, and becoming learners of mathematical practices are not attended to in the presented transcript. A missed opportunity for the development of becoming teachers of mathematics in multilingual context is seen in Turn 1 of the transcript where the teacher educator asks the PSTs what they call “tossing a coin” in their home language. It is a missed opportunity because this question could have been used by the teacher educator to enculturate the PSTs into becoming teachers of mathematics in multilingual classrooms. The different ways of naming ‘tossing a coin’ in the different languages present in the class and their meanings in English could have been interrogated in class. This would have, no doubt, enriched their discussion around the meaning of tossing a coin in mathematics.

Variation theory provides conceptual learning opportunities but such opportunities in multilingual teacher education classrooms should go hand-in-hand with language learning opportunities deliberately tied into the interactional process that occur in class. The distinction between the two roles of language as a learning medium and language as a learning goal (Lampert & Cobb, 2003; Erath et al., 2018) comes to mind. Language learning opportunities are evident when using the amalgamated framework as opposed to using only variation theory either to teach or to analyse teaching.

Finally, the question could be asked as to how the class dynamics would have been affected if, for example, a different type of communication approach or a different type of pattern of discourse was used in enacting the examples. An I-Rs₁-Rs₂-Rs₃- pattern of discourse where PSTs are given the opportunity to engage or critique one another’s solution to the problem would have enculturated the PSTs into practices that deal with judgments about what are mathematically legitimate claims, and practices such as providing justification, proving, critiquing conjectures, critiquing solutions, etc.

Concluding remarks

The triadic framework provides a multifocal conceptual lens for the exploration of three critical layers involved in the complexity of teaching and learning in mathematics teacher education multilingual classrooms. First, the mathematical object of learning needs to be central to the teaching and learning process. Regarding the object of learning, the choice of examples (using variance and invariance) needs to be such that it attends to the intended object of learning. Second, attention needs to be paid to the interactional process that takes place in the course of the enactment of the object of learning. Finally, in the context of teacher education, the framework provides for attention to be given to how the different dimensions involved in teacher preparation are (co-) constructed (or not).

The analysis in this paper has basically shown an inside-out approach (see Figure 3) in teacher preparation for teaching mathematics in multilingual classrooms where the starting point is the object of learning, culminating in the multiple facets of teacher education. My contention is that the choice of examples, and the accompanying interactional process need not necessarily gear towards developing the multifaceted dimensions involved in teacher education. The framework also provides for an outside-in approach where the teacher educator decides in advance what facets of teacher education to attend to at a particular point and then decides on which interactional process to use to give focus to these facets. This will in turn inform the type of examples that the teacher educator would choose to bring the object of learning into focus. In such a case, the framework suggested in this paper could be extended to professional development programmes involving multilingual mathematics teachers.

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